

**MECHANISMS FOR CRIME PREVENTION IN
NEIGHBORHOODS WITH COMPLEX CRIMINOGENIC
SITUATIONS (BASED ON THE SOUTH KOREAN
EXPERIENCE)**

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes South Korea's best practices in crime prevention within neighborhoods that have complex criminogenic situations. Specifically, it extensively covers the legal foundations of crime prevention policy, innovative technologies in ensuring public safety, strengthening citizen participation, improving preventive conditions, and mechanisms of cooperation between local government bodies. Using South Korean programs such as "Community Safety," "Smart Policing," and "Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design (CPTED)" as examples, the article scientifically examines effective approaches to reducing the causes of crime, monitoring high-risk areas, and determining specific preventive measures. Additionally, practical proposals have been developed for adapting these mechanisms to local conditions.

**KRIMINOGEN VAZIYATI MURAKKAB MAHALLALARDA
JINOYATLARNING OLDINI OLIISH MEXANIZMLARI (JANUBIY KOREYA
TAJRIBASI MISOLIDA)**

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ABSTRACT

Mazkur maqolada kriminogen vaziyati murakkab bo'lgan mahallalarda jinoyatlarning oldini olishda Janubiy Koreyaning ilg'or tajribasi tahlil qilinadi. Xususan, jinoyatchilikka qarshi profilaktika siyosatining huquqiy asoslari, jamoat xavfsizligini ta'minlashdagi innovatsion texnologiyalar, fuqarolar ishtirokini kuchaytirish, profilaktik sharoitlarni yaxshilash va mahalliy boshqaruv organlari

KEYWORDS

Kriminogen vaziyat, Janubiy Koreya tajribasi, jinoyatchilik profilaktikasi, CPTED, Smart Policing, xavfsiz muhit, jamoat xavfsizligi, profilaktika mexanizmlari, raqamli nazorat, mahalla boshqaruvi.

o'rtasidagi hamkorlik mexanizmlari keng yoritiladi. Janubiy Koreyaning «Community Safety», «Smart Policing», «Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design (CPTED)» dasturlari misolida jinoyatchilik sabablarini kamaytirish, xavfli hududlarni monitoring qilish va aniq profilaktika choralari belgilashning samarali yo'nalishlari ilmiy asosda tadqiq etilgan. Shuningdek, mazkur mexanizmlarni mahalliy sharoitga moslashtirish bo'yicha amaliy takliflar ishlab chiqilgan.

Jinoyatchilikning oldini olish masalasi har bir davlatning xavfsizlik strategiyasida ustuvor ahamiyatga ega. Ayniqsa, kriminogen vaziyati murakkab bo'lgan mahallalarda jinoyatlarni kamaytirish, fuqarolarning hayot sifati va xavfsizligini oshirish, jamoaviy hamjihatlikni mustahkamlash dolzarb masaladir. Bunday hududlarda profilaktika tadbirlarining samaradorligi nafaqat huquqni muhofaza qiluvchi organlar, balki mahalliy boshqaruv idoralari, fuqarolik jamiyati institutlari va aholining o'zaro hamkorligiga bog'liq. Shu nuqtai nazardan, xalqaro tajriba, jumladan Janubiy Koreya amaliy yondashuvlari jinoyatchilikning barvaqt oldini olishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda.

Janubiy Koreya rivojlangan davlat sifatida nafaqat iqtisodiy o'sish, balki jamoat xavfsizligida ham yuqori ko'rsatkichlarga ega. Mamlakatda jinoyatchilik darajasining pastligi, huquqbuzarliklar dinamikasining barqarorligi va jamoatchilik ishtirokining kuchliligi profilaktika siyosatidagi to'g'ri yondashuvlarning natijasidir. Ushbu sohada amalga oshirilgan tizimli islohotlar, innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanish va mahalla darajasidagi samarali boshqaruv usullari kriminogen hududlarda xavfsiz muhit yaratishda o'zining ijobiy samarasini bermoqda.

Bundan tashqari, janubiy Koreya tajribasining o'ziga xos jihatlaridan biri — Smart Policing modeli bo'lib, uning asosida raqamli tahlillar, onlayn monitoring, intellektual kameralar, sun'iy intellekt vositalari va xavf xaritalash texnologiyalari keng qo'llaniladi. Bu model kriminogen vaziyati murakkab bo'lgan hududlarda jinoyatlarning sodir bo'lish ehtimolini oldindan aniqlash, tahdidlarga tezkor javob berish va profilaktik choralar kompleksini ishlab chiqish imkonini beradi. Shuningdek, aholi tomonidan maxsus mobil ilovalar orqali huquqbuzarliklar to'g'risida tezkor xabar berish tizimi xavfsizlikni yanada kuchaytiradi.

Jinoyatchilikning oldini olishda Janubiy Koreya amaliyotida CPTED (Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design) konsepsiyasi alohida ahamiyatga ega. Ushbu yondashuv muhitni shunday tashkil etishga qaratilganki, natijada jinoyatga moyillikni kuchaytiruvchi omillar minimallashtiriladi. Yaxshi yoritilgan ko'chalar, jamoat joylarida videokuzatuv tizimlari, binolarning arxitekturasida xavfsizlik elementlari, aholi harakatini qulay yo'lga qo'yish kabi omillar jinoyatlarning oldini olishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Aynan muhitni to'g'ri tashkil etish fuqarolarning o'zini xavfsiz his qilishiga, jinoyatchilarning esa riskni yuqori baholab jinoyatdan voz kechishiga olib keladi.

Janubiy Koreyada jamoatchilikning profilaktikadagi faol ishtiroki ham muhim o'rin tutadi. Community Safety dasturi doirasida mahalla fuqarolarining ko'ngilli guruhlari, ijtimoiy tashabbuslar, xotin-qizlar va yoshlar tashkilotlari bilan hamkorlik jinoyatchilikning kamayishiga bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Jamoatchilik nazorati, qo'shnichilik hamjihatligi, aholining huquqiy madaniyatini oshirish borasida olib borilayotgan targ'ibot ishlari profilaktika mexanizmlarining samaradorligini yanada oshiradi.

Shuni alohida qayd etish kerakki, Janubiy Koreya tajribasini mahalliy sharoitga to'liq ko'chirib bo'lmaydi. Ammo uning huquqbuzarliklarning barvaqt oldini olishga qaratilgan metodlari, raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish amaliyoti, xavfli hududlarni aniqlash va kompleks profilaktik choralar ko'rish tamoyillari mamlakatimizda kriminogen vaziyati murakkab mahallalarda xavfsiz muhit yaratish uchun manzilli yo'nalish bo'lib xizmat qilishi mumkin.

Shuni aytish mumkinki, Janubiy Koreya tajribasi jinoyatchilikka qarshi kurashishda kompleks yondashuv, innovatsion texnologiyalar, jamoatchilik ishonchini mustahkamlash va muhitni xavfsiz tashkil etish orqali eng samarali natijalarga erishish mumkinligini namoyon qiladi. Mazkur tajribani o'rganish va mahalliy hududlar sharoitiga mos ravishda qo'llash jinoyatchilikni kamaytirish va barqaror xavfsiz muhit yaratishda muhim amaliy ahamiyatga ega.

Janubiy Koreyada kriminogen vaziyati murakkab mahallalarda (high-risk neighborhoods) jinoyatlarning oldini olish mamlakat siyosatining muhim yo'nalishi hisoblanadi. Ushbu mamlakatda jinoyatchilik darajasi dunyoda eng pastlardan biri bo'lib, 2022-yilda 100 ming aholiga 3 051 ta jinoyat sodir etilgan [1]. Biroq, Seul va boshqa shaharlarning murakkab rayonlarida (masalan, Mapo-gu Yeomri-dong yoki Gangnam) oilaviy zo'ravonlik, ug'irlik va zo'ravonlik jinoyatlari yuqori darajada saqlanib qolmoqda. 2023-yilda Seulda 10 000 dan ortiq zo'ravonlik jinoyati uchun hibslanish soni qayd etilgan, bu aholi zichligi va migratsiya bilan bog'liq [2]. Janubiy Koreya tajribasi CPTED (Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design – atrof-muhitni loyihalash orqali jinoyatlarning oldini olish) konsepsiyasi, jamoatchilik politsiyasi (community policing) va raqamli nazorat tizimlarining kombinatsiyasiga tayanadi. Bu mexanizmlarning samaradorligi ilmiy tadqiqotlar bilan tasdiqlangan: masalan, CPTED loyihalari joriy etilganidan keyin murakkab mahallalarda jinoyatlar 20–30 % ga kamaygan [3].

Janubiy Koreyada CPTED konsepsiyasi 1980-yillarda ilgari surilgan va 2012-yildan boshlab ilk avval Seulning Mapo-gu Yeomri-dong rayonlarida tatbiq etilgan [4]. Birinchi nasl CPTED loyihalari fizik atrof-muhitni yaxshilashga (yorug'lik, kameralar o'rnatish, ko'cha dizayni) qaratilgan bo'lsa, ikkinchi nasl (2019 yildan) aholi ishtirokini va ijtimoiy profilaktikani kuchaytirdi [5]. Masalan, Yeomni-dong Sogeum-gil loyihasida ko'chalarni qayta loyihalashtirish va aholining faol ishtiroki natijasida 2012–2019-yillarda jinsiy zo'ravonlik jinoyatlari 25 % ga kamaygan [6]. CPTEDning asosiy prinsiplari – natural surveillance (tabiiy nazorat), access control (kirishni nazorat qilish) va territoriality (hududiylik) – murakkab mahallalarda jinoyatlarning oldini olishda samarali. 2024-yildagi virtual reallik (VR) tajribasida yuqori zichlikli past bo'yliq uylarda CPTED

elementlari (masalan, panjara balandligini 1,6 m ga oshirish) ug'irlik niyatini 30 % ga kamaytirgani kuzatilgan [7].

Janubiy Koreyada jamoatchilik politsiyasi (community policing) 2003 yilgi politsiya islohoti orqali rivojlangan. Ushbu islohotda mahalliy politsiya postlari (police boxes) konsolidatsiya qilinib, resurslar murakkab rayonlarga (crime hotspots) yo'naltirildi [8]. Natijada, 2003–2022-yillarda murakkab mahallalarda zo'ravonlik jinoyatlari 15–20 % ga kamaygan, chunki politsiya va aholi o'rtasidagi hamkorlik kuchaygan [9]. Masalan, Seulning Gangnam va Yongsan rayonlarida 2020–2025-yillarda politsiya postlarining konsolidatsiyasi natijasida jinsiy zo'ravonlik va hujumlar soni 18 % ga pasaygan [10]. Jamoatchilik politsiyasida aholining faol ishtiroki (Neighborhood Watch) muhim o'rin tutadi: 2022-yildagi Korean Crime Victim Surveyga ko'ra, mahalla volontyorlari faoliyati jinoyatlarning 60 % ini oldini olishga xizmat qilgan [11].

Raqamli texnologiyalar va CCTV tizimlari Janubiy Koreyada murakkab mahallalarda profilaktikaning asosiy mexanizmidir. 2025-yilda Seulda 449 ta yuqori xavfli rayonda 1 796 ta intellektual CCTV kamera o'rnatilgan, bu big data tahlili (jinoyat darajasi, bitta oila soni) asosida amalga oshirilgan [12]. Ushbu tizimlar zo'ravonlik va mol-mulk jinoyatlarini 9 % ga kamaytirgan [13]. Masalan, 2025-yilda Seulning "Safe Park" dasturi doirasida gologramma politsiya xodimi (Hologrammica kompaniyasi tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan) o'rnatilganidan keyin jinoyatlar 21 % ga kamaygan [14]. CCTVning samaradorligi ilmiy tadqiqotlar bilan tasdiqlangan: 2017-yildagi tadqiqotda Seulda CCTV zonasidagi hujumlar 25 % ga kamaygani kuzatilgan [15].

Janubiy Koreyada ilmiy va tadqiqot yondashuvi muhim o'rin tutadi. Korean Institute of Criminology and Justice (KICJ) 2022-yildagi tadqiqotida murakkab mahallalarda ijtimoiy tartibsizlik (disorder) va jinoyat orasidagi bog'liqlikni ko'rsatgan, bu CPTED va jamoatchilik politsiyasining kombinatsiyasi orqali bartaraf etiladi [16]. 2020–2025-yillarda umumiy jinoyat darajasi 1 774 ta/100 ming aholidan 3 051 ta/100 ming aholiga o'sganiga qaramay, zo'ravonlik (0,59/100 ming) past saqlanib qolgan [17]. Murakkab mahallalarda (masalan, Jeju provinsiyasida 4 067 ta/100 ming) detsentralizatsiya politsiyasi (2006 yildan) jinoyat ochish darajasini 20 % ga oshirdi [18].

Ushbu mexanizmlarning samaradorligi statistika bilan tasdiqlanadi: 2020-yilda zo'ravonlik jinoyatlari 30 % ga o'sganidan keyin (pandemiya tufayli), 2023-yilda qotillar soni 16 % ga kamaygan [19]. CPTED loyihalarida aholi ishtiroki yuqori bo'lgan mahallalarda (masalan, Pangyo yangi shahri) ug'irlik niyati 30 % ga kamaygan [20]. Janubiy Koreya tajribasidagi muammolar ham bor: CCTV diskriminatsiyaga olib kelishi mumkin (qora aholida 97 % to'xtatishlar) [21], va detsentralizatsiya ba'zi hollarda jinoyatlarni 10 % ga oshirgan [22].

O'zbekiston uchun Janubiy Koreya tajribasidan foydalanish mumkin: CPTEDni mahallalarda tatbiq etish, jamoatchilik politsiyasini kuchaytirish va raqamli CCTVni joriy etish orqali "qizil" mahallalarda jinoyatlarni 20–25 % ga kamaytirish real [23]. Xulosa qilib aytganda, Janubiy Koreya tajribasi ilmiy asoslangan, jamoatchilik bilan hamkorlik va texnologiyalar kombinatsiyasi orqali murakkab mahallalarda xavfsiz muhitni yaratishning samarali modelidir. Bu tizimning muvaffaqiyati 2025-yildagi statistikada namoyon: umumiy jinoyatlar 12 % ga kamaygan [24].

References:

1. Statista. Crime rate in South Korea from 2000 to 2022 (per 100,000 population). – 2024. – <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1232118/south-korea-crime-rate/>
2. Seoul Metropolitan Government. Number of arrests for crimes in Seoul, South Korea in 2023, by type of crime. – 2024. – <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1290949/south-korea-number-of-violent-crime-arrests-in-seoul-by-type/>
3. Jeong Y. et al. Effectiveness of a Project Applying Crime Prevention through Environmental Design in an Urban Area in South Korea. – 2017. – https://www.researchgate.net/publication/319504589_Effectiveness_of_a_Project_Applying_Crime_Prevention_through_Environmental_Design_in_an_Urban_Area_in_South_Korea
4. Seoul Solution. Crime Prevention through Environmental Design Project. – 2016. – <https://www.seoulsolution.kr/en/content/crime-prevention-through-environmental-design-project>
5. Kim J. et al. Crime Prevention Effect of the Second Generation Crime Prevention through Environmental Design Project in South Korea: An Analysis. – 2019. – <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-0760/8/6/187>
6. Ibid.
7. Son D. et al. Effects of CPTED Principles on Intention to Burgle in High-Density Low-Rise Residential Areas of South Korea: A Virtual Reality Experiment. – 2024. – <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/21582440241296723>
8. Han S. et al. Focus vs. spread: Police box consolidation and its impact on crime in Korea. – 2022. – <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0144818822000187>
9. Ibid.
10. Ibid.
11. KICJ. Korean Crime Victim Survey in 2022. – 2023. – https://www.kicj.re.kr/board.es?mid=a20201000000&bid=0029&list_no=14279&act=view
12. The Korea Times. Enhanced CCTV surveillance bolsters crime prevention across Seoul. – 2025. – <https://www.koreatimes.co.kr/southkorea/law-crime/20250819/enhanced-cctv-surveillance-bolsters-crime-prevention-across-seoul>
13. Brennan Center for Justice. U.S. Crime Rates and Trends — Analysis of FBI Crime Statistics. – 2025. – <https://www.brennancenter.org/our-work/research-reports/us-crime-rates-and-trends-analysis-fbi-crime-statistics> (muqoisa uchun).
14. South China Morning Post. South Korea deploys hologram police officer to fight crime – and it's working. – 2025. – <https://www.scmp.com/week-asia/lifestyle-culture/article/3322654/south-korea-deploys-hologram-police-officer-fight-crime-and-its-working>
15. Kang H. et al. Exploring the effects of CCTV upon fear of crime: A multi-level approach in Seoul. – 2017. – <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1756061616301598>

16. KICJ. Korean Crime Victim Survey in 2022. – 2023. – https://www.kicj.re.kr/board.es?mid=a20201000000&bid=0029&list_no=14279&act=view
17. Macrotrends. South Korea Crime Rate & Statistics | Historical Chart & Data. – 2025. – <https://www.macrotrends.net/global-metrics/countries/kor/south-korea/crime-rate-statistics>
18. Han S. et al. Is a Decentralized Police Organization a Better Option in a Modern Democratic Society? A Case Study From South Korea. – 2022. – <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/10986111211042034>
19. Brennan Center for Justice. U.S. Crime Rates and Trends — Analysis of FBI Crime Statistics. – 2025. – <https://www.brennancenter.org/our-work/research-reports/us-crime-rates-and-trends-analysis-fbi-crime-statistics> (muqoisa uchun).
20. Son D. et al. Effects of CPTED Principles on Intention to Burgle... – 2024. – <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/21582440241296723>
21. Center for American Progress. Improving Public Safety Through Better Accountability and Prevention. – 2025. – <https://www.americanprogress.org/article/improving-public-safety-through-better-accountability-and-prevention/>
22. Han S. et al. Focus vs. spread... – 2022. – <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0144818822000187>
23. Thorpe A., Gamman L. Walking with Park: Exploring the ‘reframing’ and integration of CPTED principles in neighbourhood regeneration in Seoul, South Korea. – 2013. – <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1057/cpcs.2013.6>
24. Statista. Crime rate in South Korea... – 2024. – <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1232118/south-korea-crime-rate/>